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Title: SOP for replacing GC column of GC Q – Exactive

Date: 19.8.2021

Version: version 2

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IMPORTANT:

- Fore Vacuum : 5e-02 mbar
- UltraHigh Vacuum: 1.5e-10 mbar
- MS transfer line temp. (°C) 250
- Ion source temp. (°C) 280

TO prepare QC Q-Exactive for replacing column

1. In Q Exactive tune software, place instrument in the **OFF** state (*see Figure 1*)

Figure 1 Instrument OFF State Icon

2. Cool the GC oven, transfer line and source
 - a. On the GC panel, press the „**Instrument control**” and then „**Oven**” to open submenu and set „**OFF**” in temperature setpoint window
 - b. On the GC panel, press the „**Maintenance**” to open temperature menu change both **X-line 1** and **X-line 2** (transfer lines) to „**YES**” and press „**Begin Cooldown**”

Figure 2 Touch Screen Main Menu: Instrument Control

Figure 3 Oven Temperature Control Menu

Figure 4 Touch Screen Main Menu: Maintenance

Figure 5 Maintenance Temperature Menu

- c. In Q Exactive tune software, set MS transfer line temperature to **40 °C** and ion source temperature around **175 °C** (avoid excessive oxidation of source parts or contamination from the source plug).

Figure 6 MS Transfer Line and Source Temperature Control

- d. Turn the carrier gas flow of front inlet Off (Instrument Control> Front Inlet (SSL) > Column flow > Off)

NOTE: Wait until system is cooled down otherwise the column will be destroyed

3. Using the source removal tool and vacuum interlock, remove the ion source. (follow the instructional video “R2_15_Remove Cartridge.mp4” and “SOP_GC_Q_Exactive_Ion Source Maintenance.docx” for more details)

Figure 7 Placing the ion Source Cartridge in the Source Holder

4. Place the ion source cartridge on the source holder and put aside (on the desk covered with aluminium foil)
5. Place the source plug in the source plug holder *see Figure 8* and then use the source exchange tool to attach the source plug placed in the source plug holder *see Figure 9*

Figure 8 Source Plug in the Source Plug Holder

Figure 9 Attaching the Source Plug to the Source Exchange Tool

6. Twist the Plug Exchange Tool until engraved grooves on the Plug Exchange Tool and on the Source Plug align securely *see Figure 10*

NOTE: !Be sure that the Source Plug is clean and without any dust particles on it. In that case, use compressed air to blow all particles off the source plug if needed before inserting!

Figure 10 Attached Source Plug to the Source Exchange Tool

7. Insert the barrel end of the source exchange tool into the vacuum interlock (***Chyba! N enalezen zdroj odkazů.***) and twist it clockwise to lock it into the position. The black handle must be fully extended and locked. (follow the instructional video “R2_16_Install Cartridge.mp4” and “SOP_GC_Q_Exactive_Ion Source Maitenance.docx” for more details)

Figure 11 Inserting the Source Plug into the Vacuum Interlock

Figure 12 Source Exchange Tool attached with Source Plug and connected to vacuum interlock

8. Once the source plug is inside the ion source chamber, leave the source plug attached to the source exchange tool and the source exchange tool connected to vacuum interlock **see**

Figure 12

Siltite μ -Union connection of two capillary columns

NOTE: see video: <https://www.restek.com/en/video-library/connecting-GC-columns-using-a-siltite-micro-union/>

NOTE: Tools for connecting GC column with GC guard column:

- **GC column: Rxi-5Sil MS (15 m; 0.25 mm ID) RESTEK**
- **GC guard column: Rxi Guard Column (2 m; 0.53 mm ID) RESTEK to inlet**
- **GC guard column: Rxi Guard Column (2 m, 0.25 mm ID) RESTEK**
- **Ferrule, SilTite; Replacements for MicroUnion; P/N 23896 (0.25-0.53 mm) RESTEK for GC guard column 0.53 ID**
- **Ferrule, SilTite; Replacements for MicroUnion; P/N 23894 (0.25-0.25 mm) RESTEK**
- **Connector, Siltite MicroUnion; P/N: 23885 RESTEK**

Figure 13 Tools for connecting GC column with GC guard column

1. Slide the male μ -connector end fitting onto the capillary column. If you are connecting columns with different diameters, it is recommended to start with larger one first.
2. Insert the capillary column into the double taper ferrule and screw the male μ -connector end fitting into the position. Make sure the capillary column seats inside the ferrule all the time. Gently tighten male μ -connector end fitting with your fingers until you feel resistance **see Figure 14**.
3. Slide a FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tool over the capillary via the slot cut in the tool and place it on the male μ -connector end fitting. Tighten male μ -connector end fitting until the ferrule begins to hold onto the capillary column, then tighten a bit more (about 60 °).

NOTE: !Ferrule must hold onto the capillary column, but don't overtighten it!

Legend

1. Ferrule/nut adaptor tool
2. Connection nut
3. SilTite double taper ferrule
4. Capillary tubing (0.36 mm OD)
5. Male μ -connector end fitting
6. FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tool

Figure 14 Exploded view of installing male μ -connector and fitting and double taper ferrule

Figure 15 Detail of male μ -connector and fitting and double taper ferrule

4. Unscrew the ferrule/nut adaptor tool from the male μ -connector end fitting
5. Slide the female μ -connector end fitting onto the capillary column.
6. Insert the second capillary column into the double taper ferrule and screw the female μ -connector end fitting into the position. Make sure the capillary column seats inside the ferrule all the time. Gently tighten female μ -connector end fitting with your fingers until you feel resistance *see Figure 15*.

Legend

- 3. SilTite double taper ferrule
- 4. Capillary tubing (0.36 mm OD)
- 5. Male μ -connector end fitting
- 6. FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tool
- 7. Female μ -connector end fitting

Figure 16 Exploded view of Installing female μ -connector end fitting and double taper ferrule

Figure 17 Detail of female μ -connector end fitting and double taper ferrule

7. Slide a FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tool over the capillary via the slot cut in the tool and place it on the female μ -connector end fitting. Tighten female μ -connector end fitting until the ferrule begins to hold onto the capillary column, then tighten a bit more (about 60°).

NOTE: !Ferrule must hold onto the capillary column, but don't overtighten it!

8. Remove both of the FingerTite μ -connector male/female end fitting tools from the male and female μ -connector end fitting and the capillary columns. Once again, check if both column ends hold in the double taper ferrule. If yes, you are ready to install column into the instrument.

Capillary column installation guide

1. Use the GC transfer line handle to slide the GC transfer line away from the MS transfer line *see*

Figure 18

Figure 18 Separating the GC and MS Transfer Lines

2. Unscrew the nut and remove the current column and nut.

NOTE: !Do not forget to monitor the foreline pressure (typically $4.5e-02$ mbar) to confirm the source plug is properly sealing the transfer line!

NOTE: Cut off the old capillary and attach a septum to its end to provide a vacuum

3. Unwind an appropriate column length to insert into the transfer line along the front of the instrument
4. Insert the new column through the GC transfer line *see Figure 19*

Figure 19 Inserting the Column through the GC transfer line

5. Carefully extend column end out to allow application of the nut (**Spring loaded nut, EA QE GC, 1R120434-0020**) and ferrule (**Graphite /Vespel Ferrule 0.1-0.25mm, Pk 5, P/N 290VT221** (flat side of the ferrule faces the MS))
6. Use a scoring wafer to remove a bit of column to make a clean, perfect-cut end and wipe the column with methanol soaked-wipe after cutting

7. Carefully push the column back into the GC transfer line and keep the nut and ferrule on the column

Figure 20 Placement of the Column in the transfer line

8. Insert the column into the MS transfer line and tighten the nut until the column just resists sliding through the ferrule *see Figure 20*

Figure 20 Inserting the Column into the MS transfer line

9. Loosen the nut $\frac{1}{4}$ turn and push the column into the MS transfer line carefully until the column touches the source plug
10. Then pull the column about 1 mm away from the source plug and tighten the nut $\frac{1}{2}$ turn (depends on the fore vacuum value and leak but do not overtighten the nut) **see Figure 20**

11. Make sure the column and nut are correctly installed in the MS transfer line *see Figure 21*

Figure 21 Properly installed Column in MS transfer line

12. Pull the GC transfer line handle to the left to close it
13. Unwind the inlet guard column (0.53mm ID) end to easily connect the end to the injector
14. Insert the column through the septum (holds the nut at the position), the nut and proper ferrule (**VG1, 85% Vespel/15% Graphite Compact, 1/16, 0.8mm ID, 50-pk RESTEK**); (flat side of the ferrule faces the nut) *see Figure 22 and 23*
15. Use a scoring wafer to remove a bit of column to make a clean, perfect-cut end and wipe the column with methanol soaked-wipe after cutting (Use a magnifying glass to check the cut, repeat it if necessary. Demand for perfect cut here is more important than of the MS column end)

Figure 22 Inserting the column to injector

16. Position the column so that the end of the column extends the proper distance above the end of the ferrule (4-6 mm is recommended for SSL, 10 mm if you plan to use Split mode, 30 mm for PTV)

Figure 23 Detail of nut and column with ferrule

17. Finger-tighten the nut until it starts to grip the column plus $\frac{1}{4}$ turn (do not overtighten it)
18. Insert the EI ion source back
19. Restore MS transfer line temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) **250** and Ion source temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) **280**
20. In Thermo Q Exactive GC software put the instrument to **ON** mode
21. **Set the carrier gas on, restore both X-line 1 and X-line 2 and Front (SSL) wait at least 1 hour** then restore the oven temperature (80°C)
22. After restoring **X-line 1 and X-line 2 and Front (SSL)** temperatures and stabilizing the system check for potential leaks in Q Exactive software > Evaluate > Leak Check (check also fore vacuum). If needed, tighten changed-nuts to gain proper sealing (ideally about 5% or less, acceptable is leak 10 %), but keep in mind to not overtighten it
23. Condition the new column following manual for each column length and brand (typically 10 hours) **see Figure 24**
 - a. Open method: conditioning_method_PALAT.meth in **D:\data\GC methods in use** folder

b. Chose TRACE 1300 Series GC

Figure 24 Conditioning GC column

c. Click TRACE 1300 > Send Method to GC > Thermo Xcalibur Sequence Setup > Status > Trace 1300 Series GC > General > Start > when the system is ready > Start

24. Change source if needed and bake out the system, usually overnight (12 hours)